

Critical Examining the Relationship Between Fear and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Zamfara State of Northern Nigeria: In the Context of Insecurity

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Abstract

This study seeks to investigate the influence of insecurity on psychological well-being and academic achievement of secondary school students in volatile areas or Local government of Zamfara State, Nigeria. Two objectives with corresponding research questions were formulated to guide the study. A descriptive cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprise of all the senior secondary school students that were traumatically affected by the insecurity in the state and forced their schools relocation to Internally Displaced Camps. The total numbers of sampled respondents were 403 i.e. 202 (50.12%) male and 201 (49.88%) female. A Purposive sampling technique was used to select the traumatized students. Findings from the study revealed that Fear badly affects the brain architecture of memory and learning; students who confront fatal and chronic fearful experiences often lose their learning; due to which they were mentally disturbed. Finally, it was recommended the need for proper implementation of effective counselling services to address the problems and were the situations become chronic referral services of expertize like clinical psychologists were recommended for addressing the problems.

Keywords: Insecurity, Banditry, Trauma, Emotional problems, Psychological distress and Academic achievement.

Introduction

Education is a necessary tool for the emancipation of people and a catalyst for the effective realization of dreams set to achieve in the future by any given country. Its acquisition is of utmost importance in the prevention of the rising of insecurity in Nigeria and any other part of the world. Vambe, (2016), associates education acquisition with genuine wealth and happiness and the overall development of society both socially, politically, economically, and all other areas of human endeavours, whereas lack of it that involves prevalence of insecurity aggravates one's level of ignorance and lead to blunders, poverty, unhappiness, and to the commission of crimes and other social ills likely bribery and corruption that crippled the society from reaching their goals both scientifically and technologically. Therefore, poor educational development tends to have an association between poverty and poor health conditions that diminishes opportunities for social and economic advancement which often leads to criminality in all forms. In this situation, it is common to find the emergence of militant groups, thugs, and bandits that may involve in terrorist activities likely to threaten the emotional and Psychological well-being of many secondary school students.

More so, Education is essential and necessarily needed in providing security and overall safety in the entire society for example in the military and para-military organizations which includes the police that are saddled with the security of the nation. In the military, it helps the armed forces to appraise situations, estimate the battlefield, and examine the courses of action, to interpret the international environment, to project future warfare and design the battlefield and requirement to analyse security threats. With this incidence ability to provide security in the nation and quench any possible uprising depend on well-planned education system. Therefore, effective planning and executing for a sound education that cater the needs of the society would contributes to national development, and at the same time enhances national security that enhance overall development of the learners.. Therefore, from the above, it will be right to say that the higher a nation attains to insecurity, the stronger the nation's education. Hence, security contributes to the wellbeing of the citizen and education of the nation, and is a determinant of the quality of education rendered.

However, insecurity in Zamfara State that involved attacks on secondary schools tends to have a significant impact on students' psychological well-being, academic performance, and overall development. Hassan, (2014), viewed insecurity as a negative feeling characterized with fear, anxiety, uncertainty and injustice, among others. Those students who are always

afraid of insecurity and they feel fear all the time, they are suffering from insomnia and nightmares they become physically, psychologically and emotionally confused and as a result they hardly pass academically and always show poor learning as well as academic performance (Osofsky, Cohen & Drell, 1995). It is well observed that students' dropout rate increase due to fear of school attacks that may either come in the form of kidnapping and abduction, target killing, and threat (Joshi & O'Donnell, 2003). Students psychologically and emotionally suffer due to fear of insecurity associated with school attacks (Freh, Chung & Dallos, 2013). Most of the students suffer from high levels of stress and depression because of increasing fear of insecurity that involves attacks on education, develop trauma, and show sign of psychological problems in their lives. As a result, they either show poor academic performance or school phobia (Shahar, 2009).

Literature Review

School safety is indispensable and crucial for determining students' achievement, psychological well-being, and balance as well as for students' engagement (Cornell & Mayer, 2010). (Cavallaro, et al., 2012) found that students exposed to insecurity express fear and also suffer from insomnia; which discourages many students from attending school regularly due to fear, even if they may not be victims of the insecurity or terror, for that reason students were not ready to attend school because of fear of insecurity. (Bachman, Randolph & Brown, 2011) explained that poor educational achievement that may likely cause students to drop out of school is related to an increased fear exposure by insecurity. (Cavallaro, 2023) asserted that students in fear are mentally disturbed and abstracted and can't pay full attention on their studies because their minds are diverted from studying and they always think that they may be any time under attack. (Henrich et al. 2004) found that when students are exposed to insecurity in their classrooms, then their attention is diverted out of the class to something else, and remain unable to focus in class. (Chen & Chen 2020) in their conducted recently opined investigated that when students feel unsafe at school, their responses are toward their homes and missing school facilitated the development of school-phobia. This development affects students negatively particularly their academic achievement; similarly the attendance of students also negatively suffer due to fear.

However, during a period of insecurity exposing students to various atrocities and other traumatic events, can contribute in the prevalence of mental disorder among students thus threatening their well-being and emotional development (Steel, et'al 2009). Under the

prevalence of insecurity students may find it difficult to attend school regularly and engage in both curricular and extra-curricular activities related to schools. The possibility to develop school-phobia and other behaviour that may not commensurate with schooling are common among such students (Csóti, 2003).

However, prevalence of insecurity is associated with mental disorder such disorder affect the feelings of safety and students' academic achievement (Delaney-Black et al. 2002; & Gibson, Morris & Beaver, 2009). (Cavallaro, J. et al., 2012) found that schools were under the target of terrorists attacks mostly by bombings in which the school facilities damaged fully and death of dozens of students occurred; as a result students may face serious challenges such as students confronted attention, cognitive and emotional difficulties because of fear of insecurity due to which they showed poor academic score at secondary school level. Fear of violence cause upsets on students' academic performance (Delaney-Black et al. 2002; & Gibson, et al. 2008). (Schwartz et al. 2005) examined that fear of violence within schools cause serious havoc on school attendance, increases misbehaviour that fail to commensurate with learning and the development of positive attitude towards schooling and this negatively affect academic achievement among students. (Brezina & Wright, 2000) explained that the majority of the students exposed to insecurity in school carry weapons for protection against any danger and this may divert their attention which directly affects their academic achievement. (Cavallaro, et al., 2012) described that students were psychologically destabilized in school were not in a position to excel academically better due to fear of insecurity in school.

Similarly, (Delaney, Black, et al., 2002) described that students under fear and violence show poor academic performance; fear negatively affects the I.Q level and ability of students to perform academically better at School level. (Henrich, 2004) explained that fear is associated with the desire of students to achieve low grade in exam at all level of education be it primary, secondary or tertiary institution. (Margolin & Gordis, 2000) examined that students are always disturbed emotionally in fear and in such situations their ability to develop positive attitude towards schooling suffers a lot. (Glew, et al., 2005) explained that fear among students affects student ability to focus and excel academically better. (Ratner, et al., 2006) asserted that increase in fear decreases the school attendance of students due to which fearful students, mostly misses their classes and deprive from learning opportunities because of which they either hardly pass or place in low grade. (Williams et al., 2002) explained that

fear among students encourages high rates of crimes also and such students don't take interest in their studies; sometimes such type of students are mostly drug addicted and they always confront lower grades in their academic subjects due to which their dropout rates also increase.

(Irfanuddin & Khan, 2016) have pointed out that parents don't send their children to school where there is insecurity either within the school or on the way linking students to school. (Cavallaro, et al., 2012) have pointed out that as terrorism was on the peak in North Waziristan Agency and no home was kept safe from this curse so everybody was feeling to live in the hell instead of living in their homes because every family was afraid of war hazards even cars, markets, bazaars, terrorists' shelters and homes of common people were targeted in North Waziristan in order to get their target as soon as possible; in such fearful atmosphere and circumstances, it was impossible for the students even to think about learning. (Irfanuddin & Sher, 2013) found that students in North Waziristan Agency were so fearful that they were living miserable lives; they couldn't attend such activities which were in the form of congregation because they were afraid of terrorism and bomb blasting

Objectives of Study

The following were the objectives of the study:

- I. To examine how the insecurity trigger fear among secondary school students in Zamfara state.
- II. To investigate the relationship between fear and students' academic achievement as a result of insecurity prevailing among secondary school students in Zamfara State

Research Design

The current study is descriptive in nature and all the research variables were measure/analyzed by using the statistical tools.

Population and Sampling Technique

The population of the study used in this study comprises of the entire secondary school students both boys and girls that were affected by insecurity in the Zamfara State. Sample in research refers to a portion or part of the entire study population that are representative of the entire population, while sampling means the process of choosing representative portions of the population for a particular study. To reduce systematic bias, a sampling plan known as

rule of thumb was employed for better representativeness based on published tables and applying formulas to calculate sample size.

Sample Size

The population was divided into two strata by classifying them into male and female. The total numbers of respondents (n = 403). Respondents taken among Male Secondary Schools (n = 202). Respondents taken from Female Secondary Schools (n = 201).

Sample Size Rule of Thumb

10-100 100%

101-1000 10%

1001-5000 5%

5001-10000 3%

10000 + 01%

Source: Curry, J. (1984). Professor of Educational Research, North Texas State University; Sample Size Rule of Thumb; Populations and Sampling, 7-4

Data Collection

The researcher personally gathered data from 403 respondents (202 male students and 201 Female students) regarding the influence of insecurity on psychological well-being and academic achievement of secondary school students in Zamfara State of Northern Nigeria. The researcher administered an open-ended questions to a sample of 403 students from different secondary schools within the Internally Displaced Camps in Zamfara State, Nigeria on a scale of 1-5. The data produced was numerical in nature providing an information regarding the influence of insecurity on their wellbeing and academic achievement.

Collection Instrument

The researcher collected data through face-to-face questionnaire from the respondents in Zamfara State of Northern Nigeria.

Measurement Scale

Scale	Numerical Values
Always	5
Frequently	4
Occasionally	3
Seldom	2
Never	1

Pilot Study

To achieve the construct validity and the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot test was conducted with a sample of experienced students similar to the main study population. A sample of fifty (50) senior secondary school students participated in the pilot testing. The sample size comprised of males and females in the five selected schools within Internally Displaced Camps. Prior to the field administration of the instruments for validation purposes, a number of processes were followed which included content validation by experts in psychology, test and measurement and curriculum planning, identification of target population for the pilot study, selecting an appropriate sample, administration of the instrument draft, and reliability analysis as reported. To examine the internal consistency reliability of the research instrument in this study, the data collected from the pilot testing were used to conduct a test of the reliability of the instrument using the Rasch Measurement procedure. The data from the pilot test were analysed using WINSTEPS 3.72.3. The results of the analysis provided preliminary information on the suitability of the research instruments.

Reliability

The reliability coefficients revealed the item reliabilities of 0.99, with corresponding Cronbach Alpha of 0.84. These parameter was considered satisfactory reliability because according to Hair, Rolph Anderson, Ronald & Tatham (1995), a Cronbach's alpha scale greater than 0.70 is acceptable for the internal consistency reliability of the items and can therefore be accepted for research purposes. These criteria served as the guidelines in interpreting the internal consistency-reliability coefficients in the study.

Results

Table 1

Table 1: Respondents’ Views Regarding Fear Due to Insecurity in Zamfara State (n=403)

Students Response						
Scale Used						
Gender	Never	Seldom	Occasionally	Frequently	Always	Total
Male	30(14.85%)	34 (16.83%)	70 (34.65%)	42 (20.79%)	26 (12.87%)	202 (50.12%)
Female	82 (40.79%)	61 (30.34%)	39 (19.40%)	11 (5.47%)	08 (3.98%)	201 (49.87%)
Total	112 (27.8%)	95 (23.57%)	109 (27.04%)	53 (13.15%)	34 (8.43%)	403(100%)

Table 1 shows that out of total respondents (N= 403 respondents, 202 (50.12%) were male and 201 (49.88%) were female). Among male students 26 (12.87%) students always suffered from ‘Fear’ due to insecurity in Zamfara State; 42 (20.79%) students frequently suffered; 70 (34.65%) occasionally suffered; 34 (16.83%) seldom suffered and 30 (14.85%) never suffered due to In Zamfara State. Likewise, among female respondents (n=201); 08 (3.98%) always suffered; 11 (5.47%) frequently suffered; 39 (19.40%) occasionally suffered; 61 (30.34%) seldom suffered and 82 (40.79%) always suffered because of insecurity associated with schooling. As a whole in both genders i.e. male and female (n=403) respondents, the numbers of respondents always suffering from war insecurity associated with schooling were 34 (8.43%); respondents frequently suffered were 53 (13.15%); occasionally suffered were 109 (27.04%); seldom suffered were 95 (23.57%); and respondents never suffering from associated with schooling were 112 (27.8%) respectively.

Table 2: Correlation between Fear and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Zamfara State (n=403)

Psycho-traumatic problems Due to Insecurity associated with schooling	Mean	SD	r	Sig
Fear	2.2457	1.33335	-.902**	.000

Table 2 demonstrates that the Mean value of Fear is 2.2457, S.D = 1.33335, $r = -.902^{**}$ and $p = .000$. As 'p' value is less than 0.05 and 'r' value is negative. Therefore, there is negative correlation between fear and the academic achievement of in Zamfara State of Northern Nigeria.

CONCLUSIONS

Most of the students were quite fearful because of war hazards in North Waziristan due to which their leaning stamina and picking capacities were badly influenced. For that reason they either showed poor academic grades or low learning performance. They also confronted physical, mental, social and psychological dilemmas and even insomnia (sleeplessness) due to fear continuous war hazards in North Waziristan. Fear badly influenced students' mentality as well as their academic achievement at Secondary School level in North Waziristan. War hazards were fully responsible for the increasing fear in students at Secondary level in North Waziristan due to which majority of students showed poor academic performance and failing grades.

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